

Further Action of Magnesium Amalgam on Nitrates and its Action on Nitrous acid, and Salts of the Oxyacids of Sulphur and the Halogens.

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The action of magnesium amalgam on nitrates has been studied by Neogi and Nandi (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 133, 1449) who have shown that, besides hydroxylamine and ammonia, hyponitrites of the respective metals are formed. Several new hyponitrites have been isolated by this method. The success of this method for the preparation of hyponitrites lies in the fact that magnesium hydroxide, which is formed as a product of the reaction, being insoluble in water, is easily removed, and unlike caustic soda formed in Divers' sodium amalgam method, does not decompose the hyponitrites obtained as a result of the reduction of nitrates and nitrites. In this paper this method of preparing hyponitrites has been extended to other metals such as thallium, beryllium, uranium, aluminium, cerium and thorium, with the hope of being able to isolate their hyponitrites. From the experimental results given below, it would be observed that uranium, beryllium and cerium yielded unstable hyponitrites, which could not be isolated in the pure condition, as their solution readily underwent decomposition during concentration. Thallium, aluminium, and thorium do not form any hyponitrites, their hydroxides being obtained in the insoluble precipitate. Hydroxylamine was obtained in solution in the case of cerium only whilst ammonia was obtained in all cases.

The action of magnesium amalgam on nitrous acid gave a very unusual though interesting result. Free nitrous acid solution was prepared by the action of ice water on liquid N_2O_3 . On treating this below 5° with magnesium amalgam, no hydroxylamine and very little ammonia were produced but magnesium nitrite was formed in the pure state, any nitrate accompanying the nitrite undergoing reduction to the latter.

The action of magnesium amalgam on the salts of the oxyacids of sulphur and the halogens was next studied. It was found that

sulphates were not reduced by magnesium amalgam. Though sulphites are reduced by zinc and hydrochloric acid, neither sulphites nor bisulphites were reduced by magnesium amalgam even at 50° even when the reduction was carried on for several hours. Thiosulphates, however, were easily reduced to a mixture of sulphite and sulphide with the evolution of hydrogen sulphide. Dithionates remained practically unaffected, whilst persulphates yielded a mixture of sulphates, the mercury being simultaneously oxidised in the process to yellow mercuric oxide.

To investigate the action of magnesium amalgam on the salts of the oxyacids of the halogens its action on chlorates, bromates, iodates, perchlorates and periodates was studied. Chlorates and perchlorates remain unaffected even at 50°. Bromates were completely reduced to bromides and iodates to iodides, no intermediate reduction product such as hypobromite being obtained even when the reduction was effected in ice-cold solutions. Potassium periodate was reduced first to iodate and then to iodide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Beryllium hyponitrite.—Magnesium amalgam was prepared according to the method of Neogi and Nandi (*loc. cit.*). The five per cent. amalgam was cut into small pieces and stored in stoppered bottles and used when necessary.

Five gm. of beryllium oxide were dissolved in hot dilute nitric acid keeping a slight excess undissolved. The resultant solution of beryllium nitrate was cooled in ice and salt and the magnesium amalgam added in small quantities. The temperature was not allowed to rise above 5°. The precipitate was filtered off in a filter pump and the solution again treated with magnesium amalgam. This was repeated three or four times and the reduction was continued until the solution was free from nitrate and nitrite. The solution did not contain any hydroxylamine or hyponitrite. The precipitate was washed with cold water and treated with dilute acetic acid (1:15) until the greater part of the precipitate dissolved. The solution responded to the tests of both beryllium and hyponitrite, showing that beryllium hyponitrite was insoluble in water. Attempts were next made to obtain the compound in the pure state but without success. Part of the solution was neutralised with ammonia in the cold but no precipitate of beryllium hyponitrite was obtained.

The acid as well as the neutral solutions were then kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid in an ice chest surrounded with ice and salt. Both the solutions gave tests for hyponitrites for one or two days but during further concentration the hyponitrite decomposed. Repeated attempts to obtain the pure hyponitrite proved equally unsuccessful owing to the decomposition of the hyponitrite when concentrated even in ice chests.

Uranium hyponitrite.—Uranyl nitrate (5–6 gm.) was dissolved in water in a beaker immersed in ice and salt. The cold solution was treated with small quantities of magnesium amalgam in the same way as in the case of beryllium. The temperature was maintained below 5° throughout. When the reduction was continued for some time, the whole of the uranium was precipitated. The solution contained hydroxylamine and also magnesium nitrite. The precipitate was washed with water and dissolved in cold dilute acetic acid (1:15) and was found to contain hyponitrite. The solution thus obtained, even when concentrated in an ice chest in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, did not yield any hyponitrite of uranium. During concentration, the solution responded to the tests for hyponitrites for one or two days; and a yellow precipitate gradually formed which, when washed and dissolved in dilute acetic acid in the cold, did not give any test for hyponitrite. The yellow precipitate was found to be uranyl hydroxide. Repeated attempts to isolate the hyponitrite in a pure condition resulted in failure, owing to the decomposition of the hyponitrite during concentration. The uranium in the hyponitrite is possibly present in the uranyl condition, for the acetic acid solution of the hyponitrite gave with ammonia or caustic alkalis the yellow precipitate of ammonium or alkali diuranate. It is very curious, however, that uranyl compounds which are so readily reduced to the uranous condition even with sulphuretted hydrogen, should remain in the uranyl condition in the presence of nascent hydrogen. Had it been an uranous compound alkalis would have precipitated uranous hydroxide which turns black on heating.

An interesting observation is that when the acetic acid solution of the hyponitrite was kept at the ordinary temperature for some hours in air so as to allow all the hyponitrite to decompose, part of the resulting solution when treated with silver nitrate yielded a reddish brown precipitate which was undoubtedly not a hyponitrite. This precipitate was washed and on examination

was found to contain only uranium and silver, and no acid. The precipitate was found on analysis to be silver diuranate. The ratio of uranium to silver actually found is 2.22:1, the calculated ratio being 2.21:1.

The same acetic acid solution after the decomposition of the hyponitrite when treated with lead nitrate solution yielded a yellow precipitate containing only lead and uranium and no acid. The precipitate on analysis was found to be lead diuranate. The ratio of uranium to lead actually found is 2.31:1, the calculated value being 2.29:1.

Cerium hyponitrite.—A concentrated solution of cerium nitrate cooled in freezing mixture was reduced with magnesium amalgam in the usual way. After reduction for about three hours the solution became free from cerium and was found to contain hydroxylamine. The precipitate was washed with cold water and taken up with cold dilute acetic acid (1:15). The acetic acid solution was found to contain both cerium and hyponitrite, thereby showing that the cerium hyponitrite is insoluble in water. On carefully neutralising the acetic acid solution with cold dilute ammonia no precipitate of cerium hyponitrite was obtained. When preserved in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid in an ice chest, the hyponitrite decomposed in a day showing the instability of cerium hyponitrite.

Reduction of the nitrates of thallium, aluminium and thorium.

In these cases no hyponitrite was formed either in the solution or in the precipitate and no hydroxylamine was obtained. The results in each case are briefly tabulated below.

Aluminium nitrate.—A solution of aluminium nitrate was treated with magnesium amalgam in the usual way. In a short time the whole of the aluminium was precipitated as hydroxide and the solution was found to contain magnesium nitrate but no hydroxylamine or hyponitrite. The precipitate on solution in dilute cold acetic acid also did not yield any hyponitrite.

Thallium nitrate.—A solution of the thallium nitrate on reduction with magnesium amalgam in the usual way yielded thallos hydroxide in solution which contained no hydroxylamine or hyponitrite. The precipitate on solution in dilute acetic acid in the cold did not give any test for hyponitrites.

Thorium nitrate.—The results in the case of thorium nitrate were analogous to those of aluminium nitrate. In a short time the

solution on reduction with magnesium amalgam became free from thorium and contained no hydroxylamine. The solution of the precipitate in dilute acetic acid gave no test for a hyponitrite.

Action of magnesium amalgam on nitrous acid.—Preparation of pure magnesium nitrite.

Hampe (*Annalen*, 1863, 125, 295) and Lang (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1863, 86, 299) prepared magnesium nitrite from equivalent quantities of barium nitrite and magnesium sulphate. Vogel (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 35, 385) studied the constitution of crystallised magnesium nitrite and his method of preparation was the same as that of his predecessors but differed only a little in details as regards the method of crystallisation. Rây (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 178) studied the action of heat on magnesium nitrite but he also adopted the same method of preparation.

The action of magnesium amalgam on free nitrous acid gave an unusual result. This can be used as a method for the preparation of pure magnesium nitrite. Nitrogen trioxide prepared by the action of nitric acid on arsenious oxide was passed through an empty wash-bottle immersed in cold water to arrest nitric acid and then through a condensing tube immersed in a freezing mixture of ice and salt where it condensed to a blue liquid. This was brought into solution with ice cold water introduced slowly into the condensing tube by means of a pipette. The solution of nitrous acid containing a little nitric acid was placed in a beaker immersed in ice and salt and was carefully treated with magnesium amalgam keeping the temperature below 5°. After some time the solution became neutral and was found to contain magnesium nitrite (and a little nitrate) but no hydroxylamine or hyponitrite. The reduction was continued until the solution ceased to give tests for a nitrate with diphenylamine. A portion of this solution after dilution with ice cold water gave on analysis by Crum's nitrometer method the following result.

1 C.c. of the solution gave 14.3 c.c. of nitrogen gas from the solution at N.T.P.

1 „ „ „ „ 14.4 „ NO „ „ „

thus showing that it was a solution of pure magnesium nitrite containing no nitrate. When the reduction was carried still further, however, hydroxylamine was formed in the solution and magnesium hyponitrite was detected in the precipitate.

This process may be adopted as a standard method for preparing pure magnesium nitrite, which, has hitherto been prepared by pre-

vious investigators by the double decomposition of barium nitrite and magnesium sulphate. In the present method it is necessary to use magnesium amalgam and not pure magnesium as the latter acts very slowly on the solution of nitrous acid and invariably yields a mixture of magnesium nitrite and nitrate. It is magnesium amalgam which reduces any nitrate formed and ensures the formation of pure nitrite.

It will be useful here to summarise the work previously done by Neogi and Nandi (*loc. cit.*) and also the results recorded in this paper on the preparation of hyponitrites, by the action of magnesium amalgam on metallic nitrates and nitrites. As has already been pointed out, this method has the advantage of the absence of caustic soda which decomposes metallic hyponitrites and therefore made it possible to isolate new hyponitrites. The following is a tabular statement of the metals of the various groups of the periodic classification, the hyponitrites of which have been isolated by this method.

TABLE I.

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li	Be*				
Na	Mg*				
K	Ca				
	Zr				
Rb	Sr				
	Cd				
Cs	Ba	Ce*			
			Pb		
					U*

Action of magnesium amalgam on chlorates, bromates, iodates, perchlorates and periodates.

Sodium and potassium chlorates.—The solution of the chlorate was acted upon by magnesium amalgam in the cold. There is no advantage in using ice water and the temperature was generally kept between 50° and 60°. It is remarkable that neither sodium nor potassium chlorate, which is reduced to chloride by heating with

The hyponitrites of these metals were not obtained in the pure condition.

zinc and dilute sulphuric acid, sulphurous acid, ferrous sulphate, zinc dust and Devarda's alloy, is reduced by such a powerful reducing agent as magnesium amalgam.

Potassium perchlorate.—A solution of the perchlorate was treated with magnesium amalgam, at 50°-60°. The resulting solution did not contain either chlorate or chloride. This is not to be wondered at as perchlorates are not reduced by the reducing agents mentioned above.

Sodium bromate.—A solution of sodium bromate was treated with magnesium amalgam in a similar manner, and was quantitatively reduced to sodium bromide.

Sodium iodate and potassium periodate.—A solution of sodium iodate was reduced by magnesium amalgam in the usual way and was found to be reduced to iodide quantitatively, the operation taking about two hours, the temperature being kept about 50°. This reaction is similar to the reduction of an iodate by zinc dust or Devarda's alloy.

A solution of potassium periodate was similarly reduced with magnesium amalgam. At first the periodate was reduced to an iodate, the latter then undergoing reduction to iodide, no iodine being liberated at any stage of the reaction.

Action of magnesium amalgam on salts of the oxyacids of sulphur.

Sodium and potassium sulphates.—A solution of either sulphate when treated with magnesium amalgam even for a whole day did not yield any sulphite or sulphide in the solution.

Sodium sulphite and bisulphite.—It was expected that sulphites in solution would be reduced to sulphide by magnesium amalgam, but a solution of sodium sulphite when acted on by magnesium amalgam for many hours at 50°-60° failed to produce any sodium sulphide. Sodium bisulphite behaved in a similar manner.

Sodium dithionate.—Otto has shown that sodium dithionate is reduced to sodium sulphite by sodium amalgam and it was expected that magnesium amalgam would produce a similar reaction, but a solution of sodium dithionate when acted upon by magnesium amalgam at 50°-60 for 6-7 hours failed to produce any sulphite or sulphide.

Sodium thiosulphate.—A solution of sodium thiosulphate was treated with magnesium amalgam in the usual manner. The result-

ing solution contained both sulphide and sulphite whilst sulphuretted hydrogen was also evolved, being formed by hydrolysis of the sodium sulphide. This reaction is similar to that reported by Spring with sodium amalgam and thiosulphates.

Potassium persulphate.—When a solution of potassium persulphate was treated with magnesium amalgam in the usual way a vigorous reaction took place. The resultant solution contained a mixture of magnesium sulphate and potassium sulphate and a precipitate of yellow oxide of mercury was formed.

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Received March 22, 1929.